

Correlation between Vitamin D levels and Inflammatory Markers of Ageing in Middle-aged Adults: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract: The potential connection between vitamin D and inflammation has garnered significant interest in recent years. Inflammageing describes the chronic, low-level inflammation that typically increases with age, contributing to the decline in physiological function and the onset of various age-related diseases. Vitamin D, known for its role in bone health, immune function, and inflammation regulation, through its various biological functions. However, limited evidence is available regarding the association of vitamin D levels with inflammatory markers such as high sensitive C-reactive protein and Interleukin - 6 in middle-aged adults. This study is done to find the correlation between vitamin D levels and inflammatory markers of ageing such as high sensitive C-reactive protein and Interleukin - 6 in middle-aged adults. A total of 174 subjects participated in this study, with 87 individuals having vitamin D deficiency and 87 having normal vitamin D levels. Serum levels of vitamin D, high sensitive C-reactive protein and Interleukin - 6 levels were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The Spearman's correlation test was used to find the correlation between vitamin D levels and inflammatory markers. Results showed no significant correlation between vitamin D levels and inflammatory markers. Present study findings reveal that vitamin D deficiency is not associated with inflammatory markers in middle-aged adults. Therefore, this study concludes that vitamin D might not influence the Inflammageing process.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Inflammation, Middle-aged adults, Interleukin-6, C-reactive Protein, Ageing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ageing is an unavoidable and natural process that impacts all living beings, marked by a decline in biological functions and an increased susceptibility to health problems. It encompasses widespread, continuous inflammation, which is associated with reduced immune function, organ failure, and age-related diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, Parkinson's disease, and cancer [1].

Inflammation and ageing are closely linked through a concept known as "inflammaging," which describes the chronic, low-grade inflammation that typically increases with age. This process is considered a significant risk factor for various age-related diseases. With ageing, the immune system undergoes changes, leading to a state of persistent, low-level inflammation [2].

Factors contributing to chronic inflammation include cellular senescence, accumulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and an increase in oxidative stress. The senescent cells, which stop dividing and accumulate with age, release pro-inflammatory factors known as the senescence-associated secretory phenotype (SASP). SASP components can induce inflammation and contribute to tissue dysfunction and the progression of age-related diseases [3].

Ageing is associated with increased oxidative stress, which damages cells and tissues. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated during oxidative stress can activate inflammatory pathways, further promoting chronic inflammation [4]. Mitochondria, the energy-producing organelles in cells, become less efficient with age, leading to the release of damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) that can trigger inflammation [5]. The ageing immune system, known as immunosenescence, exhibits a reduced ability to respond to infections and vaccines while simultaneously increasing the production of inflammatory mediators. Chronic inflammation is

implicated in the development and progression of many age-related conditions, such as atherosclerosis, type 2 diabetes, osteoporosis, and certain cancers [6].

High-sensitivity CRP (hs-CRP) is a marker of inflammation. Its levels tend to rise in response to inflammation, which can be acute or chronic. Elevated hs-CRP levels are linked to a higher risk of various age-related conditions, including cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, Alzheimer's disease, and certain cancers [7].

Research suggests that elevated CRP levels are associated with increased mortality in older adults, independent of other risk factors [8]. This association underscores the importance of managing inflammation to improve overall health and longevity.

Interleukin-6 (IL-6) is a cytokine, a type of signalling protein, that plays a crucial role in the body's immune response and inflammation. IL-6 is involved in a variety of physiological processes, including the acute-phase response to infections and tissue injuries, as well as the regulation of metabolic, regenerative, and neural processes [9].

High levels of IL-6 are linked to several age-related diseases, including cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, osteoporosis, and neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's. IL-6 promotes the production of other pro-inflammatory cytokines and acute-phase proteins, contributing to systemic inflammation that can exacerbate these conditions [10]. Ageing-related decline in mitochondrial function can lead to increased production of ROS, which in turn stimulates IL-6 production and further inflammation [11].

Vitamin D insufficiency is linked to cardiovascular diseases, autoimmune disorders, infectious diseases, cancer, diabetes, and other health conditions [12]. Lower levels of vitamin D have been connected to various aspects of ageing, mainly through its impact on cellular processes, immune function, inflammation, bone health, and cognitive function. Recent studies indicate that low serum vitamin D levels are among the most common nutritional deficiencies in India. Specifically, research from South Karnataka, India, has shown a high prevalence of vitamin D insufficiency and deficiency across all age groups and both genders [13].

Despite the limited evidence on the potential link between vitamin D deficiency and inflammatory markers (hs-CRP and IL-6) in middle-aged individuals, this study aims to investigate the correlation between vitamin D levels and inflammatory markers (hs-CRP and IL-6) in this demographic.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. STUDY POPULATION

This cross-sectional analytic study recruited 174 participants, divided equally into two groups: 87 with vitamin D deficiency and 87 with normal vitamin D levels. The participants were selected from the Medicine Outpatient Department (OPD) of a tertiary hospital, and the analysis was performed in the institute's central research laboratory. Eligibility criteria included being aged 45 to 65 years and having vitamin D levels between 30-100 ng/ml. Exclusion criteria were hypertension, diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease, liver cirrhosis, acute inflammatory or infectious illnesses, and the use of vitamin D supplements.

B. ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The institutional ethical committee approved this study (NU/CEC/2021/112). The protocol was clearly explained to all participants, and their informed consent was obtained before participation.

C. METHODOLOGY

After a brief medical history was taken, the participant's height, weight, resting heart rate, and blood pressure were recorded. Two millilitres of venous blood were drawn from the median cubital vein using aseptic precautions and placed into a vacutainer. Blood samples were centrifuged to obtain serum for biochemical analysis. Serum vitamin D, hs-CRP and IL-6 levels were measured using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) from J. Mitra Pvt. Ltd, India, following the manufacturer's protocol, with each sample's concentration determined in duplicate.

D. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Descriptive data is presented as the mean \pm SD. Correlation between vitamin D levels and Inflammatory markers was done using Spearman's correlation test. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS software, version 25.

III. RESULTS

TABLE 1

Descriptive statistics

	Vitamin D deficient group (N=87)	Vitamin D sufficient group (N=87)
Age (years)	52.13 \pm 4.16	51.05 \pm 8.01
Weight (kg)	63.01 \pm 7.86	64.08 \pm 8.56
BMI	25.43 \pm 3.26	24.75 \pm 3.96
RHR (bpm)	80 \pm 84	80 \pm 80
SBP (mmHg)	120 \pm 130	120 \pm 130
DBP (mmHg)	80 \pm 90	80 \pm 80
Vitamin D levels (ng/ml)	16.50 \pm 3.56	34.33 \pm 3.51

Data is denoted as Mean \pm SD.

Abbreviations: BMI- Body Mass Index, RHR- Resting heart rate, SBP- Systolic Blood Pressure, DBP- Diastolic Blood Pressure.

TABLE 2

Correlation of Vitamin D levels with Inflammatory markers

Inflammatory Markers	Vitamin D levels	
	r- value	p-value
IL-6 (pg/ml)	- 0.31	0.775
hs- CRP (mg/dl)	- 0.133	0.219

The Spearman's correlation test was used to analyse the data.

"r" stands for correlation strength.

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Abbreviations: IL-6- Interleukin-6, hs-CRP- high sensitive C-reactive protein.

IV. DISCUSSION

Vitamin D deficiency is recognized as one of the most widespread nutritional deficiencies globally. Besides its role in regulating calcium, it is also linked to various anti-ageing mechanisms. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between serum vitamin D levels and inflammatory markers of ageing, such as IL-6 and hs-CRP. Vitamin D has been shown to have strong anti-inflammatory effects. It helps to raise anti-inflammatory cytokines and decrease pro-inflammatory mediators [14]. The result of this study showed no significant correlation between vitamin D levels and the inflammatory markers hs-CRP and IL-6. This suggests that variations in vitamin D levels may not directly impact the levels of these specific markers of inflammation in the ageing process. While vitamin D has been associated with various health benefits, including immune function modulation, the evidence for its direct effect on systemic inflammation, as indicated by hs-CRP and IL-6, remains inconclusive. It is important to consider that a myriad of factors influences inflammation, and the relationship between vitamin D and inflammatory markers might be complex and involve other mediating variables.

In a previous study done by Sanlier N et, al., showed that vitamin D modulates the inflammatory system by regulating the synthesis of immune cells and inflammatory cytokines, both of which are critical for the pathophysiology of many immune-related disorders [15]. Vitamin D receptors (VDR) contribute to decreased activation of nuclear factor kappa B (NF- κ B), a transcription factor that promotes inflammation. This suggests that VDR has an innate suppressive role in inflammation [16]. One of the main targets of vitamin D is NF- κ B, which is blocked by vitamin D and releases pro-inflammatory cytokines via NF- κ B subsequent release. NF- κ B activation facilitates the endogenous induction of hs-CRP, so that the effects of an activator of transcription-3 may be amplified by activated NF- κ B [16].

Studies have shown that vitamin D inhibits NF- κ B activation. This inhibitory effect is obtained in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated murine macrophage cells and submissively sensitized human airway smooth muscle cells by downregulating I κ B- α phosphorylation and upregulating the inhibitor of NF- κ B (I κ B- α) [17]. Vitamin D has been shown to downregulate the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α), and interferon-gamma (IFN- γ). This can reduce overall inflammation and the acute phase response, leading to lower levels of markers like hs-CRP [18]. Vitamin D promotes the production of anti-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-10 (IL-10). This shift towards an anti-inflammatory profile helps in modulating the immune response and reducing inflammation [19].

Vitamin D influences the activity and differentiation of immune cells such as T cells and macrophages. It promotes the differentiation of naïve T cells into regulatory T cells, which have anti-inflammatory properties. It also affects macrophage function, reducing their pro-inflammatory activity. Antioxidant properties of vitamin D can reduce oxidative stress, which is often linked to inflammation. By mitigating oxidative stress, vitamin D helps in lowering inflammatory markers [20].

There is some evidence suggesting that vitamin D might have an anti-inflammatory effect and could potentially reduce levels of hs-CRP and IL-6. However, the findings are not consistent across all studies. The relationship is likely complex and influenced by multiple factors. Further research, particularly large-scale randomized controlled trials, is needed to clarify the effects of vitamin D on these inflammatory markers.

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that vitamin D might not influence biological ageing by modulating inflammatory markers in middle-aged adults. This highlights the complexity of the relationship between vitamin D, inflammation, and ageing, and suggests that other factors or mechanisms might be more significant in the context of age-related inflammation and biological ageing in this demographic. Further research is necessary to explore these relationships in different age groups and to identify potential interventions for modulating inflammation and ageing.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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